

Website for IT Job Seekers in Oman: A Study on Bridging the Qualification Gap between Academe and Industry

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Abstract:

The project is an online system designed to provide a means of bridging the qualification gap between the academe and the industry in Oman by identifying reasons for the acceptance and non-acceptance of applicants for IT positions. It will therefore also be a means for companies to advertise vacant job positions related to IT and for job applicants to submit applications for these positions. Staff of the human resources department in these companies can use this site to get the right person by seeing their educational attainment, certificates, and experiences that the applicant possesses. This project will be designed for Omani job seekers/applicants within Oman only and for companies located in Oman seeking for applicants for IT-related jobs. The project will include the following users: the admin (administrator of the system/website), the companies looking for applicants, and the applicants or job seekers. The admin will manage all administrative functions of the system like adding of companies and deleting users (companies, applicants) if needed. The companies will post job vacancies, and approve or reject applicants according to their qualifications. The company can print listings of applicants and also individual reports of applicants. And the applicants will view job postings and apply for them. They can view the status of their applications which may be any of the following: “Pending”, “Accepted”, or “Rejected”. The system will be designed to make the posting of jobs and the application processes easy, organized, efficient, and fast for all users. The project methodology will be the waterfall model which includes the steps such as Data Gathering, Requirements Analysis, Design, Implementation, and Testing Phase. The developers will be guided by these methodologies to be able to come up with reliable research and an effective system that will meet the requirements of the project.